

Physicochemical and biological studies on manganese(II)- and zinc(II)-norfloxacin complexes

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Complexes of Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} with norfloxacin, an antibacterial drug, have been prepared and screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Norfloxacin [1-ethyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)quinoline-3-carboxylic acid] (1) is an antibacterial drug¹. The aim of the present work is to study the stereochemistry and biological activities of the complexes of norfloxacin with Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} .

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The complexes are microcrystalline and soluble in methanol and DMF. The presence of coordinated acetate ion and water molecules was confirmed by IR data. IR spectra of the Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes reveal bands at ~ 3300 , ~ 1600 , 830 cm^{-1} assigned to OH stretching, bending and rocking vibrations, respectively, which indicates the presence of water molecules in the complexes. The ligand band at 1575 cm^{-1} (C=O) shifted by $\pm 15\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating the coordination through this group. In the far-IR region, the chelates show new medium intensity bands at $\sim 482\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M-O)³. In the Zn^{II} complex additional bands at 1577, 1492, 1448, 1358 and 746 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$, $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ and $\delta(\text{COO})$, respectively, indicating the presence of acetate ion in the coordination sphere³. The presence of Cl^- ion in the Mn^{II} complex has been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis. The molecular weight (Rast's camphor)⁴ data suggest the monomeric nature of the complexes. The low molar conductance values suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

The Mn^{II} complex is paramagnetic at room temperature

having magnetic moment value 5.8 B.M.⁵. It shows electronic spectral bands at 13800 , 16300 , 19200 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(4G)$ (ν_1), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(4G)$, (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(4G)$ (ν_3), respectively. The ν_2/ν_1 , B and β values were found to be 1.1, 575 cm^{-1} and 0.66, respectively⁶, which are in fair agreement with octahedral geometry for the Mn^{II} complex. The lowering of B value from free-ion for the Mn^{II} complex (860 cm^{-1}) suggests covalent (49.5%) nature of bonding. An octahedral geometry is suggested for the Zn^{II} complex on the basis of elemental analysis⁷.

Table 1. Physical data of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
$[Mn(C_{16}H_{17}FN_3O_3)(Cl)(H_2O)_3]$	Brown	333	12.5	5.8
$[Zn(C_{16}H_{17}FN_3O_3)(CH_3COO)(H_2O)_3]$	White	332	15.08	Diamag.

The antibacterial activity of norfloxacin and its Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes against *E. coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Bacillus pyocyaneus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Cryosporium pannicale*, *Condida albicans*, *Tricoderma viride*, *Aspergillus flavus* were carried out by paper disc method⁸. The complexes showed enhanced activity against all the test pathogens except for *B. subtilis*. The antifungal activity of the Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complex were found to increase in the order : *T. varide* > *C. pannicale* > *C. albicans*. The results indicate that antibacterial and antifungal activity of the complexes are significantly enhanced on chelation.

Experimental

All the solvents and reagents used were of A.R. grade. Concentrated aqueous solution (in presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid) of the drug (L) in slight excess over

Note

stoichiometric M : L :: 1 : 1 ratio was added slowly with constant stirring to an aqueous solution of the metal salt (M). pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.6–6.5 and refluxed over steam-bath for 2 h. The precipitates so obtained was washed with hot distilled water, dried in an oven at $\sim 100^\circ$, stored in a desiccator over anhyd. CaCl_2 , and analyzed.

Metal and chloride were estimated by standard procedure. C, H and N were analyzed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} complex at room temperature was determined by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. Conductivity was measured in methanol and DMF at a concentration $10^{-3} M$ using an Elico CM-82 T conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer.

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